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A PROPOSED TRAINING FRAMEWORK FOR THE EASTERN CAPE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

Effective educator performance is crucial for the success of any educational system. In the Eastern Cape Department of Education (ECDoE) faces significant challenges in ensuring consistent and high-quality performance among educators. The purpose of this study is to propose a training framework tailored to address the specific needs of educators in the Eastern Cape, aiming to enhance their professional skills and ultimately improve student outcomes. The framework integrates multiple components, including needs assessment, professional development programmes, mentoring and coaching initiatives, and continuous evaluation mechanisms. Data was collected using mixed research methods. In depth interviews were used to collect data from five Human Resource Development officials of the Eastern Cape Department of Education. Survey questionnaires were used to collect data from 267 educators. Qualitative data was analysed using thematic data analysis techniques whilst descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse data from survey questionnaire. By implementing this training framework, the Eastern Cape Department of Education aims to empower educators with the necessary skills, knowledge, and support systems to excel in their roles. Through targeted professional development, mentoring, and continuous evaluation. The framework seeks to cultivate a culture of excellence and continuous improvement within the education system, ultimately leading to enhanced educator performance and improved student outcomes in the Eastern Cape Province

Keywords: training, Eastern Cape Department of Education, educator performance, human resource development, Continuous Professional Teacher Development.

Introduction

Teacher professional development programs play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education by equipping educators with the necessary skills, knowledge, and strategies to meet the diverse needs of students. In the Eastern Cape Department of Education (ECDoE), where educational challenges are prevalent, the effectiveness of these programmes is of paramount importance. The ECDoE faces various socio-economic challenges that impact its education system. Factors such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, and resource constraints contribute to the complexity of providing quality education (ECDoE Annual Report, 2022/23). Teacher professional development programmes emerge as a crucial intervention to address these challenges by empowering educators to deliver high-quality instruction and support student learning effectively.

Lack of training in schools have resulted in low performance of educators as well as students in various schools across the country. The school principals in many instances failed to understand the demands and requirement of the new curriculum resulting in the misunderstanding of important information in the teaching and learning process (Manison, 2015:100, Adams, 2022). It is more worrying that most of principals and educators are not given the opportunities to attend skill and development programmes in the province (Laskowska & Dańska-Borsiak, 2016:67; Matsepe & Maluleke, 2019:170). Several scholars agreed that most principals and educators are not well skilled and lacked knowledge in all areas of subject content (Mondy & Martocchio, 2016:56; Matsepe & Maluleke, 2019:170; Zindi & Sibanda, 2023). Even though principals are obliged to offer classroom supervisions and offer support to teachers at schools, shortage of skills and knowledge blocked them from offering the

necessary and required support needed by educators to improve their performance and learners' results (Erasmus, 2021). As a result, educators only used their knowledge and skills to interpret curriculum policies and affect them during their teaching and learning processes.

Overview of skills shortages in South Africa's education sector

The education system in South Africa lacks relevant skills in a number of areas, which negatively affect the quality of education and the general achievement of educational goals. South Africa faces numerous challenges which include lack of capacity of s workers to provide high-quality education to learners. According to Kennedy (2022) lack of skills in the education sector has a detrimental effect on the quality of education. The Annual National Assessment (2016:46) concurs that the superiority of the education system is below acceptable. The report indicates that the South African learners are not achieving its educational goals. Survey results from Rao & Hammza (2018) showed that South African students performed the lowest on the International Reading Literacy. McChesney & Aldridge (2021) express regret that while the Trends in International Mathematics and Natural Sciences revealed that South African educators attended many skill-development initiatives, student performance revealed that these efforts had no impact. It is clear from this situation that the CPTD activities are not having the desired effect of raising student and teacher performance levels.

The above-highlighted situation is also present in the ECDoE. The biggest problem of ECDoE is shortage of skills which caused by insufficient training and skills development to produce quality results in various schools. Thus, educators are anticipated to implement the curriculum as envisaged in the strategic plan, but with very limited in-service training (Carl, 2009:130). Limited participation in Curriculum and Assessment Policy (CAPS) where clear curriculum standards and goals are spelt out is often raised as a constraint to the implementation of the strategic plan of the ECDoE. According to the ECDoE Annual Report, 2022/23, there is high shortage of trained teachers in the following fields: Afrikaans, Sesotho, Accounting, Mathematics and Agriculture continue to be difficult. According to the report's further findings, there is a lack of alignment between training outcomes and employer needs, urban bias exists in institutional capacity and learning delivery methods.

Similar to other provinces, Gauteng faces a scarcity of subject matter experts in technical and vocational fields, especially in TVET colleges where there is a great need for qualified teachers in trades like automotive mechanics, plumbing, and electrical engineering (Helmbold, Venketsamy & van Heerden, 2021). Because of this, some TVET programmes do not have enough skilled instructors, which makes it harder to provide hands-on training and build industry-relevant skills. Once more, the Mpumalanga Province's educational system lacks technical and vocational abilities, especially in areas like TVET programmes, curriculum development and assessment. As a result, some TVET colleges find it more difficult to provide programmes that are in line with industry requirements and needs thereby restricting students' access to possibilities for high-quality technical education and training. Furthermore, the KwaZulu-Natal Province faces challenges pertaining to weak educational administration and management, which negatively impacts student achievement. Some schools in the province lack effective principals and deputy principals who can provide strategic direction, mentorship, and support to teachers (Raanhuis, 2021). This lack of leadership ability frequently leads to weak policy implementation, low staff morale and bad school governance.

The South African education sector lacks educational psychologists and support staff in most schools across the country. For instance, most schools in the provinces of the Western and Eastern Cape lack the number of educational psychologists and support staff needed to adequately address the social needs and behavioral issues of their students (Langeveldt, Pietersen & Van Wyk, 2023). Students' mental health and general wellbeing may be impacted by this shortfall since they may not receive adequate support to address issues such as bullying, trauma, or learning difficulties.

Furthermore, the country also lacks information and communication Technology skills and knowledge needed in the 21st century. Many teachers in areas like Mpumalanga and Limpopo are not adept at using educational technology for teaching and learning (Koukis & Jimoyiannis, 2019). The lack of ICT skills makes it difficult to incorporate technology into the curriculum and limits the opportunities for pupils to gain digital literacy and engage in 21st-century learning (Kennedy, 2022). According to a survey conducted in the province of Limpopo by Zindi & Sibanda (2023) over 70% of teachers were ill-prepared to use e-learning to teach students. In light of this, the province of Limpopo must ensure that its teachers are equipped with the necessary technological skills to attain the departmental goals. Another study by Chen, Park & Breazeal (2020) pointed out that low performance in the Mpumalanga province was a mismatch between training programmes and the curriculum of the department. This was found to pose challenges to educators in the teaching and learning process.

Conceptualising Continuous Professional Teacher Development programmes.

Continuous Professional Teacher Development (CPTD) programmes refer to systematic and ongoing initiatives designed to support educators in their professional growth, learning, and development throughout their careers

(Kennedy, 2022). Teachers can enhance their teaching techniques and grow professionally with the help of CPTD programmes. These programs are based on the idea that teaching well is a lifetime endeavor that calls for constant learning, introspection, and modification to satisfy new curriculum requirements and learner performance (Esho & Verhoef, 2020). The CPTD programmes emphasize the application of new information, skills, and methods in authentic teaching contexts and are closely correlated with classroom practice (Adams, 2021). This integration ensures that professional learning experiences are relevant, practical and immediately applicable to teachers' day-to-day work.

More significantly, CPTD's essential elements are constant feedback and reflection to allow teachers to evaluate their own performance, pinpoint areas for improvement and improve the way they teach (Raanhuis, 2021). The CPTD programmes use technology to improve professional learning experiences' flexibility, accessibility, and efficacy. Online learning environments, digital materials, webinars, online forums and learning management systems allow instructors to collaborate and share resources at any time and from any location (Nicol, 2019).

Guiding Theory- Path Dependency Theory

The Path dependence theory can be traced from the field of political science where institutional development focuses on organisational employees on how they interact and work towards the attainment of organisational goals (Peter, 2010:3). According to Fadiran (2015:26) path dependency theory draws much of its support from historical institutionalism, which views institutions as structural variables composed of different ideas, interests and powers. March & Osen (1984:15) argue that path dependency theory relies heavily on institutional policies, decisions and structures that were developed long time ago and are incorporated in the daily operation of the institution. The ECDoE follows certain structural policies, systems and procedures when training and developing its employees, which makes it difficult to accomplish the strategic plan set by the department. The ECDoE should amend its structures and find innovative ways by developing the skills of its educators and officials so that organisational goals can be achieved as envisaged in the strategic plan and vision.

Similarly, Mahoney (2000:507) views path dependency theory as characterised by historical sequences in which contingent events set into motion institutional patterns or even chains that have deterministic properties. Mahoney (2000:508), identifies two types of analysis practised by path-dependency scholars: 'self-reinforcing sequences and reactive sequences. In both types of sequences, a 'path' is a pattern of continuing behaviour, with the difference being in the causal forces shaping the pattern (Martin, 2012:180; Grube, 2016:531-532).

Path dependence theory provides a potent lens for exploring the nature and extent of alignment between the human capital development strategy and the ECDoE strategic plan (Peter, 2010). The theory allows recognition to and accounting for, the role of history and path-dependent dynamics and outcomes, as they relate to alignment between human capital development and the ECDoE strategic plan. Applied to the ECDoE path-dependency theory may account for the continued following of certain structural policies, systems and procedures for training and developing employees, which makes it difficult to accomplish the strategic plan, mission and vision.

As postulated by this theory, path-dependent institutions often get trapped within a historical structural system that continuously determines and reproduces its past activities, processes and operations for the present and future (Martin, 2012:182; Fadiran, 2015:4). As such, it would be prudent for the ECDoE to establish and operationalise a framework that aligns CPTD programmes to its strategic plan, mission and vision.

Method

The study adopts a pragmatic research philosophy and a mixed- methods approach which uses both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to propose a training framework that can be adopted by ECDoE to improve its trainings. The quantitative strategy and positivist paradigm were adopted to collect data, from purposefully two hundred and sixty-seven (n=267) educators using a survey questionnaire. The interpretivist research philosophy informed the qualitative strategy. In-depth interview data was collected from five (n=5) HRD officials purposefully sampled information-rich participants to a point of data saturation. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis.

Findings

The collected data from both interviews and survey questionnaires showed that ECDoE educators lack relevant and adequate training to improve their performance in the teaching and learning process. In support of the above, Hartley (2017:20) a large number of teachers in the Eastern Cape region lacked the necessary teaching expertise, which negatively impacted students' academic performance. As a result, teachers must execute the curriculum in

accordance with the strategic plan, but with little in-service training (Carl, 2009:130). The Primary School Reading Intervention Program (PSRIP) and curriculum development are two examples of the training programs that the ECDoE has been delivering. However, because these programs are only available to a small number of educators, they do not address the capacity and skill shortages within the ECDoE. The ECDoE Annual Report (2022/22:30), expresses concern over the fact that only 94 teachers from eight (8) districts received training in the Primary School Reading Intervention Programme and 1000 teachers only in the 12 districts received training on the Grade 1-3 Methodology content module and eight subject advisors and thirty-six Grade 1 teachers received training on phonics.

However, because these trainings only have room for a small number of educators, the majority of educators do not receive any training at all, and as a result, the ECDoE is relatively silent about how to develop other educators inside the organization (Zindi & Sibanda, 2023). Insufficient training and professional development for educators in the province has resulted in poor performance of educators and learners in critical subjects such as Accounting, Physical Science, Mathematics, Afrikaans and Sesotho in the province (Rao & Hammza 2018:242). The ECDoE's strategic plan advocates that the organization should develop high-quality education and learning using highly skilled and professional educators and that all educators should have equal access to and use of departmental resources (ECDoE Strategic Plan, 2020-2025). Despite having stated that as one of its strategic objectives, the ECDoE has fallen short of expectations; the bulk of educators have been left behind while a small percentage of educators have gotten training.

The available data points that in the provincial skill development strategy for the Eastern Cape there is insufficient training and skills development to produce quality results in various schools. Bearing in mind that poor performance and service delivery, the Auditor General Annual reports has attributed this to lack of adequate and necessary skills to perform the jobs.

Discussion

Many educators in the ECDoE are short of pedagogical skills and content knowledge that are critically important in performing their duties and improve learner performance. This was further aggravated by limited participation in CAPS raised constraint to the implementation of the strategic plan of ECDoE. The ECDoE needs to adopt the following framework for aligning strategic plan priorities with its human capital development strategies. Data collected from the interviews and survey questionnaires led to the development of a proposed training model below.

Developed by the Author

Effectiveness of training

The ECDoE need to implement skill development programmes to increase the performance of its educators as stated in its strategic plan. Esho & Verhoef (2020:16) states that effectiveness of training measures the impacts of training on the trainee's knowledge, skills, performance and the organisation's productivity. In addition, the training goals and objectives should be determined before training occurs, allowing training goals to be clearly and accurately measured. Measuring the impact and effectiveness of training ensures that the training in the organisation runs necessary, effectiveness and efficient. It enables the organisation to match the cost it has outlaid in the training's design and implementation with the associated benefits with its employees and the organisation receive. Effectiveness of training can be done through identifying employee training needs, designing learning programmes, collecting feedback from trainers and educators (Zindi & Sibanda, 2023).

Communication is very important in informing educators about the purpose of the training and the expected outcomes of training during the training programmes. Matsepe & Maluleke, (2019:171) is of the view that trainees need to be fully informed about the importance and the purpose of the training and the end products of training, so that they are able to cascade the training to others who were not able to attend. Training programmes should not be seen as a chance to enjoy the extracurricular activities that comes with the training such as stipend and rewards after attending training sessions rather it should be viewed as a way of acquiring new knowledge and skills to improve work performance (Chakraborty & Biswas, 2020).

It is important to ensure that professional development programmes correspond with educators needs and Key Performance Areas. CPTD programmes should be tailored to the needs of the educators and should support the development of new skills and improved job performance (Prummer, Human-Vogel & Pittich, 2023). The ECDoE must do a thorough examination of each individual's needs before planning training programs that are appropriate for the professional development of educators. In order to provide educators with the necessary knowledge and abilities to help them achieve the departmental goals outlined in the strategic plan, it is critical that public sector institutions adopt skills development programs (Felton & Stickley, 2018:67).

Strategic Plan Alignment

Kools & George, (2020:263) defines strategic plan alignment as a process of planning and implanting practices to ensure an organisation's strategies or objectives are accomplished. A strategically aligned organisation involves operations, methods and prescribed practices that work together to achieve long term organisational goals (Bryson & George, 2020:12). It is important that senior leaders should implement and monitor the planning life cycle and link key operational systems and processes to the organisational's mission, vision and objectives. A strategic alignment process begins with clear long- term goals, objectives that must be accompanied to ensure organisation the organisation achieve its goals and mission. The perceived benefits of strategic plan alignment in the ECDoE denote the extent to which strategic plan alignment adds value to employee performance. Given the importance of the dimensions of strategic plan alignment to employee performance, the ECDoE must develop and implement all-inclusive HRD strategy that will enlighten their actions.

Furthermore, the HRD strategy will determine how the HR process will run and how to ensure that it serves its purpose to support the organisation to accomplish their aim (Nicol, 2019). When the strategy has been set up, it will be the rudimentary groundwork on how HR section can strategise and executive their obligations at all echelons. By taking an all-inclusive assessment of the entire organisation, human resource strategy gives prospect to total matters obstructing the achievement of organisational objectives. The ECDoE can adopt a comprehensive strategy to improve the performance of educators as well as achieving the objectives as envisaged in the Strategic Plan.

Furthermore, George, Drumaux, Joyce & Longo, (2020) argue that the development of the strategic plan should be designed for the future, be formally documented, and the results be summarised, synthesised and reported in a strategic plan thematically and holistically. Formality is an important consideration in the pursuit of strategic management, because greater formality is usually positively correlated with the cost, comprehensiveness, accuracy, and success of planning (Drumaux & Joyce, 2020:8). The main reason for documentation of strategic planning process is to keep the organisation's core beliefs, aspirations and philosophies. Formal strategic planning is a formalised practice to produce an articulated outcome in the form of an integrated structure of decisions and concentrate on formalisation of the activities of strategy design or formulation. At stage two, the strategic planning process can be revised to see if the vision, mission and guiding principles are still valid for the goals and objectives of the organisation (DoE, 2020:54). Strategic plan alignment is equally important in the training of educators, as it ensures that teaching and learning initiatives are integrated with the broader goals and vision of educational institutions.

Educational institutions have specific missions and visions guiding their activities. Aligning educator training with these overarching goals ensures that educators are equipped with the skills, knowledge, and pedagogical approaches necessary to effectively implement the institution's mission and vision (Kools & Stoll, 2016:19; Bryson & George, 2020:39). Strategic alignment in educator training emphasizes student-centered approaches to teaching and learning. Elliott (2020:22) pointed out that Educators are trained to focus on the needs, interests, and learning styles of their students, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes and student success.

Drumaux & Joyce (2020:10) emphasized that Educator training aligned with strategic plans enables teachers to develop and implement curriculum that is in line with educational standards and objectives. This ensures consistency in instruction and helps to achieve desired learning outcomes across all levels of education. Educational landscapes are constantly evolving, with new trends, technologies, and methodologies emerging. Joyce (2017) affirms that strategic alignment in educator training allows institutions to adapt to these changes effectively by providing educators with the necessary professional development opportunities to stay current and innovative in their teaching practices.

Inclusive education and diversity are increasingly important considerations in educational settings. According to Jacobsen & Johnsen (2020:19) strategic plan alignment ensures that educator training addresses issues of diversity, equity and inclusion, empowering educators to create inclusive learning environments where all students feel valued and supported. Strategic plan alignment emphasizes the importance of data-driven decision-making in education. Educator training provides teachers with the skills to collect, analyze, and utilize data to inform instructional practices, identify areas for improvement, and monitor student progress towards learning goals (Drumaux & Joyce, 2020:21).

Strategic plan alignment in educator training supports the professional growth and development of teachers throughout their careers. George, Walker & Monster (2019) opine that by providing ongoing training and support that is aligned with institutional goals, educators are better equipped to meet the evolving needs of their students and the broader educational community. Educational institutions often seek to foster partnerships with parents, community organizations, and other stakeholders to support student learning. Jacobsen & Johnsen (2020:20) mention that strategic plan alignment in educator training includes opportunities for educators to develop skills in community engagement and collaboration, strengthening ties between the school and the broader community.

In conclusion, strategic plan alignment in educator training ensures that teachers are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and support they need to effectively contribute to the achievement of educational goals and objectives. By aligning educator training with the broader strategic direction of educational institutions, educators can better meet the needs of diverse learners and prepare students for success in an ever-changing world.

Evaluation of training

The ECDoE should play a critical role in assessing whether skills development programmes are bringing the desired outcomes or not. Felton & Stickley, (2018:58) argue that it is very important to understand different training evaluation models and methods and apply the most suitable ones to enable an organisation to improve the effectiveness of the training and organisational performance. The main purpose of evaluating a training program is to gain knowledge about whether it has achieved or failed its objectives. Evaluation of training provides a systematic method to study a program, practice, intervention, or initiative to understand how well it achieves its goals (Nicol, 2019).

Firstly, when conducting any training, it is very essential to clearly define the objectives and desired outcomes. These objectives should align with the educational priorities and needs of the Eastern Cape region. For instance, the objectives can include strategies to improve including improving teaching methodologies, subject knowledge and addressing specific challenges faced by educators in the Eastern Cape province. Adam (2021:36) emphasises that conducting a pre-training assessment allows for the identification of baseline knowledge, skills, and needs among educators. This assessment can take the form of surveys, interviews or observations to gather information about current practices and areas for improvement from educators.

During the training phase, it is important to monitor the delivery of the training programme to ensure that it meets the intended objectives. This involves providing ongoing support to trainers, addressing any logistical issues and collecting feedback from participants to gauge their satisfaction and engagement (Rao & Hammza, 2018). Following the completion of training, assessments should be conducted to measure the extent to which participants have acquired new knowledge and skills. This involves administering quizzes, exams, or performance evaluations to gauge changes in educator practice and student outcomes. More importantly, soliciting feedback from participants is essential for understanding their perspectives on the training experience. This feedback can

be gathered through surveys, focus groups, or interviews, and should encompass aspects such as the relevance of the content, the effectiveness of the delivery, and suggestions for improvement (Esho & Verhoef, 2020:16).

However, evaluating training does not end once the training programme is completed. It is important to monitor the implementation of new practices and strategies in the classroom to assess their sustainability and impact over time (Chakraborty & Biswas, 2020). This may involve classroom observations, student assessments and feedback from school administrators. Ultimately, the effectiveness of educator training should be measured by its impact on student learning outcomes. This involves analysing standardized test scores, graduation rates and other indicators of student achievement to determine whether the training has led to improvements in educational outcomes in the Eastern Cape.

Evaluation of training should be an ongoing process aimed at continuously improving the quality and effectiveness of educator training programs. This involves using feedback from participants and stakeholders to refine training materials, delivery methods, and content to better meet the needs of educators in the Eastern Cape. By systematically evaluating training programs for educators in the Eastern Cape, the Department can ensure that professional development initiatives are effectively meeting the needs of educators and ultimately improving student outcomes in the region

Employee Performance

Zindi & Sibanda (2023) define employee performance as how employees fulfill their duties and execute the required tasks. Employee performance also contributes to the assessment of how valuable an employee is to the organisation therefore, individual performance drives organisational performance. Matsepe & Maluleke, (2019:79) mention that employees need to understand the organisational vision and goals, how their work fits into the organisation, and how they contribute to mission of an organisation. Effective performance management is essential to an organisation. Evaluating educator performance is a critical aspect of ensuring quality teaching and learning outcomes. The following approaches can be used to evaluate educator performance in the Eastern Cape

Before implementing training programs, it is essential to conduct a needs assessment to identify areas where educators require support and development. This assessment includes input from educators themselves, as well as feedback from school administrators, parents, and students (Raanhuis, 2021). By understanding the specific needs of educators in the Eastern Cape, training programs can be tailored to address those areas effectively. Once needs have been identified, targeted training and support programmes can be developed to address areas of weakness and enhance areas of strength among educators. These training programmes should provide opportunities for ongoing professional development, mentoring, coaching, and peer collaboration. Training should be practical, relevant, and aligned with the specific challenges and goals of educators in the Eastern Cape.

It is crucial to implement formative assessment strategies, such as classroom observations, peer evaluations, and self-assessment tools, can be used to provide ongoing feedback to educators on their performance (Hartley, 2017:20). This feedback should be constructive, specific, and actionable, highlighting areas of strength and areas for improvement. Regular feedback sessions can help educators reflect on their practice and make adjustments to enhance their effectiveness in the classroom. Educator performance evaluations should be based on a variety of data sources, including student achievement data, classroom observations, and educator self-assessments (Chen et al., 2020). By analyzing data trends over time, education authorities can identify patterns of effectiveness and areas for intervention. Data should be used not only for accountability purposes but also to inform targeted professional development efforts and support educators in improving their practice. Recognizing and rewarding high-performing educators can serve as a powerful motivator and incentive for continued excellence. This includes awards, honors, promotions, or other forms of recognition for educators who demonstrate outstanding performance in the Eastern Cape. Additionally, incentives such as opportunities for career advancement or additional professional development can help to retain talented educators and encourage continuous improvement.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the proposed training framework for the Eastern Cape Department of Education represents a comprehensive and strategic approach to addressing the professional development needs of educators in the region. By establishing clear standards, conducting needs assessments, providing targeted training and support, and collecting and analyzing data, the framework aims to enhance educator performance and ultimately improve student outcomes. This framework emphasizes the importance of aligning training initiatives with broader educational goals and priorities, ensuring that professional development efforts are focused on areas of greatest need and relevance to the Eastern Cape context. By investing in the continuous professional growth and support

of educators, the Department of Education can foster a culture of excellence and innovation in teaching, leading to positive impacts on student learning and achievement.

Furthermore, the framework recognizes the importance of ongoing evaluation and feedback in informing continuous improvement efforts. By regularly assessing the effectiveness of training programs and educator performance, education authorities can identify areas of success and areas for refinement, leading to more targeted and impactful professional development initiatives in the future. In essence, the proposed training framework represents a proactive and collaborative approach to supporting educators in the Eastern Cape, empowering them with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to excel in their roles and positively impact the lives of students across the region. Through strategic implementation and a commitment to excellence, the Department of Education can work towards building a stronger and more resilient education system that meets the needs of all learners in the Eastern Cape.

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